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Research Article

A TRANSVERSE RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE DISTRESS AND ANXIETY AMONG WORKING DOCTORS WITH RESPECT TO DEMOGRAPHIC FEATURES**Dr. Aswad Mustafa, Dr. Muhammad Ahmed, Dr. Faizan Javed**
Punjab Medical College Faisalabad**Abstract**

Objectives: The main purpose of this research work is to evaluate the anxiety & distress among doctors in accordance with the impacts of the features of demography.

Methodology: This transverse research work carried out at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from February to August 2017. All the participants of the research work were doctors with a minimum six-year service. HADS inventory (Standardized Hospital Anxiety Depression Score) chose as inventory. The ethical committee gave the approval for the conduction of the research work. All the participants gave the written consent to participate in the research work. Demographic traits of all the doctors documented as autonomous variables; wariness & distress scores being the variables of the outcome. SPSS software version twenty was in use for the analysis of the data. Chi-square method was in use for cross tabulation, a P value of less than 0.05 was significant.

Results: Out of two hundred and three willing persons, only ninety-seven participants gave a response. The anxiety score was 7.04 ± 4.470 ; greatest score being nineteen, depression scores was 4.94 ± 3.605 , greatest score being fifteen. Mild to medium anxiety & depression was present in thirty-three and twenty-four doctors correspondingly, while seven and one doctors had serious anxiety & depression correspondingly. There was a clear association between anxiety & depression. There was an important impact of the years of service on the depression & sex on the anxiety, nine men and twenty-four women had the anxiety from mild to moderate while four men and three women had the serious anxiety and other variables did not show important effects on the scores of HADS.

Conclusion: High grades of anxiety & depression were present in the doctors. All the doctors require prompt monitoring and administration in all the organizations.

Keywords: HADS, organization, depression, distress, anxiety, wariness, response, moderate, mild, impact.

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INTRODUCTION:

In recent times, every individual is aware of the anxiety and depression terms. No area of the world is free from these problems [1]. Proper health of mind is very important for every person to pass a good life. Anxiety & depression have negative effects on the personal and occupational life of the people [2]. Most of the people especially doctors are not willing to get treatment for these issues. Systematic evaluation of the issues of mental health with anxiety & depression is not a common practice. This subject shows that the countries which are under development are containing the 2/3 psychiatric patients of the whole world [3]. The problems of the mental health of the doctors are not concerned by normal people as well as by the doctors themselves. Although considerable research has carried out in the countries of the modern world as United States of America & Canada to assess the mental condition of the doctors the developing countries are much behind this progress [4].

In Pakistan, there are very few studies about these topics. Some works showed that twenty-five to thirty percent of Karachi population was suffering from these issues of anxiety & depression [5]. Other research work also concluded a high occurrence of anxiety & depression among family practitioners working in Karachi [2]. Some works concluded that the danger of depression and suicidal ideas are two times greater in doctors as compared to the normal people of the society [6]. HADS was in use for the measurements of the scores for the further management of these problems [7].

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work carried out at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from February to August 2017. Doctors with less than 6 months of

service, history of the depression or facing some other serious diseases or mental illness were not part of this research work. The non-probability purposive method was in use for the selection of the samples. Standardized HADS (Hospital Anxiety Depression Scale) was in use as a screening instrument.

The doctors were from both genders and from different departments of the same hospital. The ethical committee of the hospital gave the approval for the conduction of the case study and doctors gave the written consent to participate in the research work. The rate of no response was fifty percent; the needed size of samples was ninety-six describing a population of twenty thousand. So, two hundred and twenty demographic forms & inventory of HADS circulated to the willing doctors. SPSS software was in use for the analysis of the collected information and percentages or rates were in use for the expression of the qualitative information.

RESULTS:

Out of two hundred and twenty willing doctors, ninety-seven gave a response. The average age of the doctors was 33.47 ± 9.45 years. Fifty-two were males and forty-five were females. The rates of other demographic and service traits are available in Table-1 & 2. Anxiety & depression scores are present in Table-3. There was a pure association between the scores of anxiety & depressions. The effect of sex on the scores of anxieties was also important, nine men and twenty-four women found with anxiety from mild to moderate while four men and three women had serious anxiety. There was no effect of the marital condition of the doctors as well as a number of their children, age, qualification, years of service, working hours and income in rupees in every month has no impact.

Table – I: Service Traits

Service Traits	Number	
Service Length (Years)	10 to 14	7
	15 to 19	7
	Above 20	19
Type of Job	Medical Officer Clinical	17
	Trainee	23
	Consultant	25
Current Employment	Civilian Doctor	41
Per Week Duty Hours	96 to 125	13
	126 to 175	37
	175 to 245	19
Additional Assignments	Resident	45
	On Call from Home	16
	Resident MO2 + On Call from Home	9

Table – II: Demographic Characteristics

Demographics		Number
Age Group (Years)	22 to 29	44
	30 to 39	26
	40 to 49	16
	50 to 59	10
	Above 60	1
Marital Status	Single	33
	Once Married	64
	Divorced	0
	Widowed	0
	More than Once Married	0
Children	Nil	48
	1	9
	2	11
	3	21
	Above 4	8
Qualification	MBBS	61
	MCPS And/Or MPH	4
	MSc And/Or MPH	5
	Single FCPS Or Equivalent	21
	>1 FCPS Or Equivalent	6
Monthly Income	Nil	15

(Thousands PKR)	15 to 49	31
	50 to 74	21
	75 to 99	6
	Above 100	24
Social Class	Low	2
	Low-Middle	4
	Middle-Middle	48
	Upper-Middle	33
	Upper Class	8

Doctors with less service had a higher score in depression, 11.46% of doctors had less than four-year service and 8.3% doctors had five to nine year of service. The effect of the sex, marital condition, number of their children, per day working duration, other related duties and income in rupees for every month was not of much importance.

Table – III: Frequency & Percentage of Anxiety and Depression

Category	Grade	Number	Percentage
Anxiety	Mild	20	20.6
	Moderate	13	13.4
	Severe	7	7.2
Depression	Mild	19	19.6
	Moderate	5	5.1
	Severe	1	1

DISCUSSION:

A large amount of the population does remark to have depression and anxiety in their lives at any time. But most of them feel hesitate to go under treatment. Most of the patients want to get rid of the treatment. The abnormalities of the mental health not always accepted by the patients in the whole world because of the terror of stigmatization. Anxiety is a severe state of worry [8], which can because of unhappy condition, unwanted physical and medical symptoms [9]. The no mood and disgust to enter in the daily activities is depression [10]. The patients of these problems always have bad physical and mental health and they have the danger to developing the disorders of the personality [2]. Even doctors are also not free from these problems.

A mentally unhealthy doctor cannot provide his services efficiently as compared to the doctors in full healthy state [2]. The occurrences of these problems in the doctors were not under consideration in past [6]. HADS was in use for the evaluation of the seriousness of these problems and other participating features. HADS is a comprehensive tool for the evaluation of depression & anxiety [11]. Zigmond & Snaith [12] developed this method. None of the doctors discovered with the anxiety or depression has undergone proper administration. There is no data present about these issues in doctors of our country but some literature displays that thirty-nine percent family practitioners in the city of Karachi had these issues [2]. There is a strong association between anxiety and depression which is similar to the other research works [4].

In this research work, more females were the victims

of anxiety as compared to male, but there was no important effect of the sex on the scores of depressions. Research works concluded that females have more danger to develop these problems [4, 13], the ideas of suicide and mental depression [14], and six times more dangerous than males' doctors according to research work conducted in the city of Karachi [2]. In this research work, depression was a close relationship with the years of the service but the service years have no impact on the scores of anxieties. In the UK, the experienced doctors had great amounts of the metal depression [15]. In another study, fifty percent new doctors were facing the problem of emotional disturbance [16]. Marriages are declared as unhappy in some research work because doctors are more committed to their professions [6].

A great amount of the workload, a great number of working hours, a high number of patients, legal and moral issues are some of the features that are the contributing factors in anxiety and depression [2]. In Karachi, there was a relation among depression & anxiety as well as more than forty-eight working hours in every week [2]. Another research work proved that doctors working more than forty-six house in a week have the danger to developing the mental abnormalities [14]. In Turkey, doctors with low income have the danger to develop the anxiety [4]. Prevention is the best cure to eliminate these issues in doctors [2].

CONCLUSION:

Doctors are also the also the victims of anxiety & depression. They should be truly monitored on a

regular basis in their lives for the presence of anxiety & depression to avoid bad impact on their health.

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